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**I. INTERNATIONAL TECHNOLOGY
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ANALYSIS OF THE 2021 CALLS OF THE TUBITAK 1702 PATENT-BASED TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER SUPPORT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the content, scope, and outcomes of two calls opened in 2021 within the TÜBİTAK 1702 Patent-Based Technology Transfer Support Program and evaluate them in the context of national development and technology diffusion. The study examines concepts such as patents, commercialization, and national development. It also analyzes the commercialization of patents from the perspectives of firms, patent owners, and national economies. Additionally, the study investigates the state support and incentives provided for the commercialization of patents through a review of international literature. The study employs content analysis to examine the changes introduced in the 2021 calls of the 1702 Patent-Based Technology Transfer Support Program. It also investigates the locations where the commercialized projects are located. The results show that in the 1st Call, 50% of the projects were commercialized in the same province, 16.66% in neighboring provinces, and 33.33% in different provinces. In the 2nd Call, 56.52% of the projects were commercialized in the same province, 9.10% in neighboring provinces, and 30.43% in different provinces. The study concludes that the 1702 program, launched by TÜBİTAK at the national level, indicates that technology diffusion occurs at the regional rather than national level.

Keywords: TÜBİTAK 1702, Patent-Based Technology Transfer Support Program, Commercialization, Regional Development